

**IMPACTS OF INVESTMENTS ON REGIONAL AND LOCAL
DEVELOPMENT; THE CASE OF ROME, ITALY**

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Abstract

The article aims to present the impact of the investments made on the local and regional scale for the development of the city of Rome in Italy. The study uses the survey method to get the perspective and the responses of the communities associated with tourism and how investments can develop the areas in Rome. As per the survey, investments in the tourism sector create new opportunities for the economy to grow, create new job positions, enhance the infrastructure and services associated with it in the city, and groom the image of the city on a global scale.

Keywords: Government investments, tourism, developments, foreign direct investment.

Introduction

From the beginning tourism industry in Italy has been developing for decades, and the tourism sector has continued the advancements in the economy. Newer regions and areas have been established in Italy; the most significant one is Rome, the country's capital city (Branchini, 2015). The investments within the European region's tourism sector have led to developments in Rome. Most of the country's GDP resides upon the tourism sector, as the revenue generated reached a significant \$52 billion in 2019. The policies in the tourism sector are developed frequently to develop the investments and eliminate the factors leading to the industry's downfall (Valeri, 2015).

City	Tourists	Rank	Change
Rome	10,317,000	#17	+2.5%
Milan	6,604,400	#40	+1.9%
Venice	5,590,500	#48	+1.6%
Florence	5,125,700	#52	+1.3%

Table 1. Statistics of tourists in Italy

Fig-1. Co-relation between employment and tourism in the region

Rome is the Republic of Italy's capital and the capital of the Lazio region that surrounds it, becoming a creative political. From its creation, a center for the arts in 753 BC of the Roman Empire formally the Roman Empire lasted into the eighth century. Despite a decline in the early medieval and late empire periods. Rome, albeit returned as an important center for politics and culture (Ali et al., 2014).

Site	Type
Coliseum and the Fora	Ancient Ruins/Museum
Vatican Museums and St. Peter's Basilica	Museum, Church/Religious Institution
Pantheon	Church/Ancient Ruins
Villa Borghese Gallery	Museum
Capitoline Museums	Museum

Fig-2. Top destinations in Rome for tourism

Italy resides in the best tourist destinations, including Rome, Milan, Venice, and Pisa; however, out of the bunch, being the capital Rome is on the top of the list of foreign tourists to begin their journey in the country. The tourism sector represents an essential part of the Italian economy, and many sectors are to be developed to establish a social and cultural differentiation among the tourist destinations (OECD, 2021). Tourism investments in the city of Rome develop new opportunities for jobs in the region, as numerous businesses in the region reside

Fig-3. Contribution to the GDP through tourism

upon the tourism sector. Rome is considered the ancient masterpiece of the Roman Empire, and other historical destinations are also the center of attraction for tourists. The regional developments lead toward infrastructural development on regional and local scales (World Wildlife Fund, 2009).

Research on the importance of investments in a region

In the survey conducted in 2010 for the tourism sector in Italy, the value of the industry generates income through different channels, including hotels, transportation on a regional, local and international scale, as well as food and beverage as these are among the leading attractions for the tourists representing the cultural and social environment of the region. As per the survey, the internal tourism sector in Italy generated about USD 155 billion (Istat – National Institute of Statistics, 2018). This revenue has been generated from the services within the tourist destination region; the

area's economy continues to be dominated by the service sector, which is also its most significant employment.

Indicators	2017	2018
Number of International tourists (million)	15.2	15.2
Export of tourist services (million US\$)	103	113.4
Number of hotels	824	905

Table-2. Tourism in Rome

The Italian economy continues to benefit greatly from tourism economy. In the year 2017, the tourism sector contributed 13.30% to GDP and engaged 14.75% of the workforce, along with indirect roles. In the year 2018, the direct employment in the tourism sector was 2.0 million, or 8.3 percent of all employment.

Rome is a popular travel destination for visitors worldwide and has seen substantial expansion in recent years. Due to its historical and cultural riches, Rome is a popular tourist destination in Italy for tourism and business travel (Montanari & Staniscia, 2010).

The presence of tourists can help sure locals' economic and social circumstances, but it can also lead to an increase in critical factors. Historical centers' ecology, economy, and social structure are altered when the disadvantages outweigh the benefits.

Fig-5. Economic growth in Rome in the tourism sector

Year	Number of tourists	Receipts	% of GNP	Receipts per tourist
2020	38.42 m	20.46 bn \$	1.1 %	533 \$
2019	95.40 m	51.91 bn \$	2.6 %	544 \$
2018	93.23 m	51.60 bn \$	2.5 %	553 \$
2017	89.93 m	46.72 bn \$	2.4 %	519 \$
2016	84.93 m	42.42 bn \$	2.3 %	500 \$
2015	81.07 m	41.42 bn \$	2.3 %	511 \$
2014	77.69 m	45.56 bn \$	2.1 %	586 \$
2013	76.76 m	43.83 bn \$	2.0 %	571 \$
2012	76.29 m	40.94 bn \$	2.0 %	537 \$
2011	75.87 m	43.27 bn \$	1.9 %	570 \$

Fig-6. *Tourism development in the economy of the region*

Conclusion

The stats present that the lack of attention towards the tourism sector in Rome may impact the region's economic development, as it resides in numerous opportunities and small businesses which might be impacted. The investments and government interest in the sector can facilitate the region's development and influence more tourists within the area. The increase in the developments in the infrastructural sectors and the factors directly affecting the tourism sector can groom the economic strength of Rome. The greater the region is established, the more the number tourists tend to visit, and the economy of the region also develops significantly. With a "Second District" of monuments in the "Eternal City," the city of Rome hopes to attract more tourists. These attractions are unnecessary compared to the cathedrals and archaeological sites to entice both foreign guests and those who have already been to Rome but would only return for a brand-new experience. Hence, Rome's vice mayor, Mauro Cutrufo, asserted that the city had 1 million more visitors in 2010 than in 2009, and that number is likely

to treble in 2011. By an astounding 400, Rome could draw in the Chinese market. Rome still tries to compete with Paris and London's activity and arrivals despite the 14 million visitors it welcomed in 2010.

Fig-6. Beautiful scenery of the city of Rome

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